

“QUYOSH TIZIMIDAGI SAYYORALAR” ELEKTRON MAJMUA YARATISH TEXNOLOGIYASI

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Kalit soʻzlar: Axborot texnologiyalarini umumtaʼlim maktablari taʼlim jarayoniga tatbiq etish. Oʻzbekiston Respublikasida internet rivoji mamlakat taraqqiyoti bilan uzviy bogʻliqligi. Oʻquv jarayonida axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanishni rivojlantirishda masofali oʻqitish. Pedagogik texnologiya oʻzida xususiyatlari.

Annotatsiya: Hozirgi kunda elektron darslik va majmualarni bir necha xil tayyorlash usullari mavjud. HTML tili imkoniyatlaridan foydalanib ham elektron majmua tayyorlash mumkin. Bu sohaning hozirda imkoniyatlari kengaygan. HTML sahifalari tayyorlovchi va ularga bezak berish imkonini beruvchi maxsus dasturlar ishlab chiqilgan. Bunday dasturlarga misol sifatida Autoplay, Microsoft FrontPage, Dreamweaver dasturlarini keltirish mumkin. Bu dasturiy vositalar yordamida astronomiya fanidan elektron oʻquv qoʻllanma tayyorlandi.

unit Unit1;

interface

uses

Windows, Messages, SysUtils, Variants, Classes, Graphics, Controls, Forms,

Dialogs, StdCtrls, Buttons, ExtCtrls;

type

var

Form1: TForm1;

implementation

uses Unit2, Unit3, Unit4, Unit5, Unit6, Unit7, Unit8, Unit9;

{ \$R *.dfm }

procedure TForm1.BitBtn1Click(Sender: TObject);

begin

form1.Visible:=false;

form2.visible:=true;

end;

procedure TForm1.BitBtn2Click(Sender: TObject);

begin

form1.Visible:=false;

form3.visible:=true;

end;

procedure TForm1.BitBtn3Click(Sender: TObject);

begin

form1.Visible:=false;

form4.visible:=true;

end;

procedure TForm1.BitBtn8Click(Sender: TObject);

```
begin
form1.Visible:=false;
form5.visible:=true;
end;
procedure TForm1.BitBtn7Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
form1.Visible:=false;
form6.visible:=true;
end;
procedure TForm1.BitBtn6Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
form1.Visible:=false;
form7.visible:=true;
end;
procedure TForm1.BitBtn5Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
form1.Visible:=false;
form8.visible:=true;
end;
procedure TForm1.BitBtn4Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
form1.Visible:=false;
form9.visible:=true;
end;
procedure TForm1.FormCreate(Sender: TObject);
begin
end;
end.
var
  Form2: TForm2;

implementation
uses Unit1;
{$R *.dfm}
procedure TForm2.Button1Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
form2.Visible:=false;
form1.visible:=true;
end;
procedure TForm2.Label1Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit1.Text:=Floattostr(6.28*58*exp(6*ln(10)))+ ' km';
end;
procedure TForm2.Label2Click(Sender: TObject);
```

```

begin
edit2.Text:=floattostr(36*exp(22*ln(10))*6.67*exp((-
11)*ln(10))/sqr(2.439*exp(6*ln(10))))+' m/s^2';
end;
procedure TForm2.Label3Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit3.text:=floattostr(4*3.14*sqr(2439))+' km^2';
end;
procedure TForm2.Label4Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit4.text:=floattostr(3.14*sqr(2439)*2439*4/3)+' km^3';
end;
procedure TForm2.Label5Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit5.Text:= floattostr(36*exp(13*ln(10))/(3.14*sqr(2439)*2439*4/3))+' kg/m^3';
end;
procedure TForm2.Label6Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit6.Text:= floattostr(0.205*58*exp(6*ln(10)))+' km';
end;
procedure TForm2.FormCreate(Sender: TObject);
begin
end;
end.
var
  Form3: TForm3;
implementation
uses Unit1;
{$R *.dfm}
procedure TForm3.Button1Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
form3.Visible:=false;
form1.visible:=true;
end;
procedure TForm3.Label1Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit1.Text:=Floattostr(6.28*108*exp(6*ln(10)))+' km';
end;
procedure TForm3.Label2Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit2.Text:=floattostr(48*exp(10*ln(23))*6.67*exp((-
11)*ln(10))/sqr(6.051*exp(6*ln(10))))+' m/s^2';
end;
procedure TForm3.Label3Click(Sender: TObject);

```

```

begin
edit3.text:=floattostr(4*3.14*sqr(6051))+' km^2';

end;
procedure TForm3.Label4Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit4.text:=floattostr(3.14*sqr(6051)*6051*4/3)+' km^3';
end;
procedure TForm3.Label5Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit5.Text:= floattostr(48*exp(14*ln(10))/(3.14*sqr(6051)*6051*4/3))+' kg/m^3';
end;
procedure TForm3.Label6Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit6.Text:= floattostr(0.0068*108*exp(6*ln(10)))+' km';
end;
procedure TForm3.FormCreate(Sender: TObject);
begin
end;
end. unit Unit4;
interface
uses
  Windows, Messages, SysUtils, Variants, Classes, Graphics, Controls, Forms,
  Dialogs, StdCtrls;
type
  TForm4 = class(TForm)
    Label1: TLabel;
    Label2: TLabel;
    Label3: TLabel;
    Label4: TLabel;
    Label5: TLabel;
    Label6: TLabel;
    Edit1: TEdit;
    Edit2: TEdit;
    Edit3: TEdit;
    Edit4: TEdit;
    Edit5: TEdit;
    Edit6: TEdit;
    Button1: TButton;
  procedure Button1Click(Sender: TObject);
  procedure Label1Click(Sender: TObject);
  procedure Label2Click(Sender: TObject);
  procedure Label3Click(Sender: TObject);
  procedure Label4Click(Sender: TObject);

```

```

procedure Label5Click(Sender: TObject);
procedure Label6Click(Sender: TObject);
procedure FormCreate(Sender: TObject);
private
{ Private declarations }
public
{ Public declarations }
end;
var
  Form4: TForm4;
implementation
uses Unit1;
{$R *.dfm}
procedure TForm4.Button1Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
form4.Visible:=false;
form1.visible:=true;
end;
procedure TForm4.Label1Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit1.Text:=FloatToStr(6.28*150*exp(6*ln(10))+' km';
end;
procedure TForm4.Label2Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit2.Text:=floattostr(59.8*exp(10*ln(23))*6.67*exp((-
11)*ln(10))/sqr(6.371*exp(6*ln(10))))+' m/s^2';
end;
procedure TForm4.Label3Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit3.text:=floattostr(4*3.14*sqr(6371))+' km^2';
end;
procedure TForm4.Label4Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit4.text:=floattostr(3.14*sqr(6371)*6371*4/3)+' km^3';
end;
procedure TForm4.Label5Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit5.Text:= floattostr(59.8*exp(14*ln(10))/(3.14*sqr(6371)*6371*4/3))+' kg/m^3';
end;
procedure TForm4.Label6Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit6.Text:= floattostr(0.017*150*exp(6*ln(10))+' km';
end;
procedure TForm4.FormCreate(Sender: TObject);

```

```
begin
end;
end. unit Unit5;
interface
uses
  Windows, Messages, SysUtils, Variants, Classes, Graphics, Controls, Forms,
  Dialogs, StdCtrls;
type
  TForm5 = class(TForm)
    Label1: TLabel;
    Label2: TLabel;
    Label3: TLabel;
    Label4: TLabel;
    Label5: TLabel;
    Label6: TLabel;
    Edit1: TEdit;
    Edit2: TEdit;
    Edit3: TEdit;
    Edit4: TEdit;
    Edit5: TEdit;
    Edit6: TEdit;
    Button1: TButton;
  procedure Button1Click(Sender: TObject);
  procedure Label1Click(Sender: TObject);
  procedure Label2Click(Sender: TObject);
  procedure Label3Click(Sender: TObject);
  procedure Label4Click(Sender: TObject);
  procedure Label5Click(Sender: TObject);
  procedure Label6Click(Sender: TObject);
  procedure FormCreate(Sender: TObject);
  private
    { Private declarations }
  public
    { Public declarations }
  end;
var
  Form5: TForm5;
implementation
uses Unit1;
{$R *.dfm}
procedure TForm5.Button1Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
form5.Visible:=false;
form1.visible:=true;
```

```

end;
procedure TForm5.Label1Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit1.Text:=Floattostr(6.28*4499*exp(6*ln(10))+' km';
end;
procedure TForm5.Label2Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit2.Text:=floattostr(102*exp(10*ln(24))*6.67*exp((-
11)*ln(10))/sqr(25.05*exp(6*ln(10))))+' m/s^2';
end;
procedure TForm5.Label3Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit3.text:=floattostr(4*3.14*sqr(25050))+' km^2';
end;
procedure TForm5.Label4Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit4.text:=floattostr(3.14*sqr(25050)*25050*4/3)+' km^3';
end;
procedure TForm5.Label5Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit5.Text:= floattostr(102*exp(15*ln(10))/(3.14*sqr(25050)*25050*4/3))+' kg/m^3';
end;
procedure TForm5.Label6Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit6.Text:= floattostr(0.0085*4499*exp(6*ln(10))+' km';
end;
procedure TForm5.FormCreate(Sender: TObject);
begin
end;
end. unit Unit6;
interface
uses
  Windows, Messages, SysUtils, Variants, Classes, Graphics, Controls, Forms,
  Dialogs, StdCtrls;
type
  TForm6 = class(TForm)
    Label1: TLabel;
    Label2: TLabel;
    Label3: TLabel;
    Label4: TLabel;
    Label5: TLabel;
    Label6: TLabel;
    Edit1: TEdit;
    Edit2: TEdit;

```

```
Edit3: TEdit;
Edit4: TEdit;
Edit5: TEdit;
Edit6: TEdit;
Button1: TButton;
procedure Button1Click(Sender: TObject);
procedure Label1Click(Sender: TObject);
procedure Label2Click(Sender: TObject);
procedure Label3Click(Sender: TObject);
procedure Label4Click(Sender: TObject);
procedure Label5Click(Sender: TObject);
procedure Label6Click(Sender: TObject);
procedure FormCreate(Sender: TObject);
private
{ Private declarations }
public
{ Public declarations }
end;

var
  Form6: TForm6;

implementation

uses Unit1;

{$R *.dfm}

procedure TForm6.Button1Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
  form6.Visible:=false;
  form1.visible:=true;
end;

procedure TForm6.Label1Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
  edit1.Text:=Floattostr(6.28*2871*exp(6*ln(10))+' km';
end;

procedure TForm6.Label2Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
  edit2.Text:=floattostr(87*exp(25*ln(10))*6.67*exp((-11)*ln(10))/sqr(24.8*exp(6*ln(10))))+'
m/s^2';
end;
```



```

procedure TForm6.Label3Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit3.text:=floattostr(4*3.14*sqr(24800))+ ' km^2';
end;

procedure TForm6.Label4Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit4.text:=floattostr(3.14*sqr(24800)*24800*4/3)+' km^3';
end;

procedure TForm6.Label5Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit5.Text:= floattostr(87*exp(16*ln(10))/(3.14*sqr(24800)*24800*4/3))+ ' kg/m^3';
end;

procedure TForm6.Label6Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit6.Text:= floattostr(0.047*2871*exp(6*ln(10)))+ ' km';
end;

procedure TForm6.FormCreate(Sender: TObject);
begin

end;

end. unit Unit9;

interface

uses
  Windows, Messages, SysUtils, Variants, Classes, Graphics, Controls, Forms,
  Dialogs, StdCtrls;

type
  TForm9 = class(TForm)
    Label1: TLabel;
    Label2: TLabel;
    Label3: TLabel;
    Label4: TLabel;
    Label5: TLabel;
    Label6: TLabel;
    Edit1: TEdit;
    Edit2: TEdit;

```

```

Edit3: TEdit;
Edit4: TEdit;
Edit5: TEdit;
Edit6: TEdit;
Button1: TButton;
procedure Button1Click(Sender: TObject);
procedure Label1Click(Sender: TObject);
procedure Label2Click(Sender: TObject);
procedure Label3Click(Sender: TObject);
procedure Label4Click(Sender: TObject);
procedure Label5Click(Sender: TObject);
procedure Label6Click(Sender: TObject);
procedure FormCreate(Sender: TObject);
private
{ Private declarations }
public
{ Public declarations }
end;

var
Form9: TForm9;

implementation

uses Unit1;

{$R *.dfm}

procedure TForm9.Button1Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
form9.Visible:=false;
form1.visible:=true;
end;

procedure TForm9.Label1Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit1.Text:=Floattostr(6.28*228*exp(6*ln(10))+' km';
end;

procedure TForm9.Label2Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit2.Text:=floattostr(66*exp(22*ln(10))*6.67*exp((-11)*ln(10))/sqr(3394*exp(6*ln(10))))+' m/s^2';
end;

```



```
procedure TForm9.Label3Click(Sender: TObject);  
begin  
edit3.text:=floattostr(4*3.14*sqr(3394))+ ' km^2';  
end;
```

```
procedure TForm9.Label4Click(Sender: TObject);  
begin  
edit4.text:=floattostr(3.14*sqr(3394)*3394*4/3)+ ' km^3';  
end;
```

```
procedure TForm9.Label5Click(Sender: TObject);  
begin  
edit5.Text:= floattostr(66*exp(13*ln(10))/(3.14*sqr(3394)*3394*4/3))+ ' kg/m^3';  
end;
```

```
procedure TForm9.Label6Click(Sender: TObject);  
begin  
edit6.Text:= floattostr(0.093*228*exp(6*ln(10)))+ ' km';  
end;  
var
```

```
Form1: TForm1;
```

```
implementation
```

```
uses Unit2;
```

```
{ $R *.dfm }
```

```
procedure TForm1.Label2Click(Sender: TObject);  
begin  
edit3.Text:='464';  
end;
```

```
procedure TForm1.Label3Click(Sender: TObject);  
begin  
edit2.Text:=floattostr(464*cos(10*pi/180));  
end;
```

```
procedure TForm1.Label4Click(Sender: TObject);  
begin  
edit1.Text:=floattostr(464*cos(20*pi/180));  
end;
```

```
procedure TForm1.Label5Click(Sender: TObject);  
begin  
edit4.Text:=floattostr(464*cos(30*pi/180));  
end;
```

```
procedure TForm1.Label6Click(Sender: TObject);  
begin  
edit5.Text:=floattostr(464*cos(40*pi/180));  
end;
```

```
procedure TForm1.Label7Click(Sender: TObject);  
begin  
edit6.Text:=floattostr(464*cos(50*pi/180));  
end;
```

```
procedure TForm1.Label8Click(Sender: TObject);  
begin  
edit7.Text:=floattostr(464*cos(60*pi/180));  
end;
```

```
procedure TForm1.Label9Click(Sender: TObject);  
begin  
edit8.Text:=floattostr(464*cos(70*pi/180));  
end;
```

```
procedure TForm1.Label10Click(Sender: TObject);  
begin  
edit9.Text:=floattostr(464*cos(80*pi/180));  
end;
```

```
procedure TForm1.Label11Click(Sender: TObject);  
begin  
edit10.Text:='0';  
end;
```

```
procedure TForm1.Button1Click(Sender: TObject);  
begin  
form1.Visible:=false;  
form2.Visible:=true;  
end;
```

```
procedure TForm2.Label3Click(Sender: TObject);  
begin  
edit2.Text:=floattostr(abs(464*cos(10*pi/180)-464));  
end;
```

```
procedure TForm2.Label4Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit1.Text:=floattostr(abs(464*(cos(20*pi/180)-cos(10*pi/180))));
end;
```

```
procedure TForm2.Label5Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit4.Text:=floattostr(abs(464*(cos(30*pi/180)-cos(20*pi/180))));
end;
```

```
procedure TForm2.Label6Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit5.Text:=floattostr(abs(464*(cos(40*pi/180)-cos(30*pi/180))));
end;
```

```
procedure TForm2.Label7Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit6.Text:=floattostr(abs(464*(cos(50*pi/180)-cos(40*pi/180))));
end;
```

```
procedure TForm2.Label8Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit7.Text:=floattostr(abs(464*(cos(60*pi/180)-cos(50*pi/180))));
end;
```

```
procedure TForm2.Label9Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit8.Text:=floattostr(abs(464*(cos(70*pi/180)-cos(60*pi/180))));
end;
```

```
procedure TForm2.Label10Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
edit9.Text:=floattostr(abs(464*(cos(80*pi/180)-cos(70*pi/180))));
end;procedure TForm2.Label11Click(Sender: TObject);
```

```
begin
edit10.Text:=floattostr(abs(464*(0-cos(80*pi/180))));
end;procedure TForm2.Button1Click(Sender: TObject);
```

```
begin
form2.Visible:=false;
form3.Visible:=true;
end;
```

```
procedure TForm4.BitBtn1Click(Sender: TObject);
begin
Memo1.Lines.Add(' ');
```

```

Memo1.Lines.Add(floattostr(0.222*cos(10*pi/180)*100*10));
Memo1.Lines.Add(' ');
Memo1.Lines.Add(floattostr(0.222*cos(20*pi/180)*100*10));
Memo1.Lines.Add(' ');
Memo1.Lines.Add(floattostr(0.222*cos(30*pi/180)*100*10));
Memo1.Lines.Add(' ');
Memo1.Lines.Add(floattostr(0.222*cos(40*pi/180)*100*10));
Memo1.Lines.Add(' ');
Memo1.Lines.Add(floattostr(0.222*cos(50*pi/180)*100*10));
Memo1.Lines.Add(' ');
Memo1.Lines.Add(floattostr(0.222*cos(53*pi/180)*100*10));
Memo1.Lines.Add(' ');
Memo1.Lines.Add(floattostr(0.222*cos(60*pi/180)*100*10));
Memo1.Lines.Add(' ');
Memo1.Lines.Add(floattostr(0.222*cos(70*pi/180)*100*10));
End;

```

Dasturiy tildagi elektron o`quv qo`llanmaning ko`rinishi Autoplay dasturida quyidagicha :

Dastur oynasidan Quyosh tizimidagi sayyoralar haqida ma`lumotning matn, audio, video, test ko`rinishdagi shakllari berilgan . Mundarija asosida masalalar, laboratoriya ishlari, glossariy vva shu bilan birga ikki xil dastur asosida sayyolarning fizik parametrlarni hisoblab ko`rsatilgan, ikkinchi dasturda esa turli geografik kengliklarda chiziqli tezlikni grad hisoblash texnikasi ko`rsatilgan.

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